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Nikfar Dominations: Definitions, Theorems, and Connections

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Abstract

Domination can be viewed axiomatically. We propose a collection of axioms that bridge the gap between several types of domination. Along the way we prove theorems about domination that satisfy our axioms and state conjectures that arise naturally from our axioms. In this article, we show how one can attach adjectives to domination (and which adjectives one should attach, as determined by one's goals) in such a way that the resulting class of dominations provide a detailed framework for understanding domination. This framework can be used to clarify the distinctions between various classes and also to unify by showing connections between them.

Keywords: domination, analytic nikfar domination, edges, dominating sets, domination number

AMS Subject Classification: 05C72, 05C69, 03E72, 94D05

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1 Introduction

In section 2, we define the following dominating sets in a fuzzy graph (see section 2 for definitions):

A *fuzzy set* on a given set V , is a map assigning to every its elements a real number from unit interval $[0, 1]$; this number is called *value* of element in V .

The *number* of a fuzzy set is a summation on values of all its elements.

A *fuzzy graph* G is an ordered pair (V, E) consisting of a fuzzy set V of *vertices* and a fuzzy set E , disjoint from V , of *edges*, together with an *incidence function* ϕ_G that associates with each edge of G an unordered pair of (not necessarily distinct) vertices of G . If e is an edge and u and v are vertices such that $\phi_G(e) = \{u, v\}$, then e is said to *join* u and v , and the vertices u and v are called the *ends* of e . In a fuzzy graph, value of every vertices are at least equal to value of their ends. We denote the numbers of vertices and edges in G by $n(V)$ and $n(E)$; these two basic parameters are called the *order* and *size* of G , respectively. In section 2, some examples should serve to clarify the definition. For notational simplicity, we write uv for the unordered pair $\{u, v\}$.

We don't speak about a graph. So when we write vertices or edges, we talk about a fuzzy graph.

A *path* is a sequence of vertices $v_0v_1 \cdots v_n$ such that $v_{i-1}v_i$ is an edge for any $1 \leq i \leq n$. The least value between edges in a path is called its value. In other words, if e has the least value in a path P , we would call $E(e)$ value of path and it is denoted by the same notation $E(P)$. In this case, we have $E(e) = E(P)$. The greatest value between all paths in a fuzzy graph $G = (V, E)$ is called value of fuzzy graph G and is denoted by $E(G)$.

2 Two views of domination

Based on the relations between edges in paths, we can define several types of a domination in a fuzzy graph. In what follows, we would tend to work on the structures of a dominating set. We would implement the notions in Ref. [1] for defining several types of concept of domination in a fuzzy graph.

3 Nikfar domination and the axioms

3.1 Analytic Nikfar Domination

The first set of domination in our discussion is defined axiomatically.

Definition 3.1. An *analytic nikfar domination* is a structure which satisfies the three axioms below. In this article we will also refer to it types, which are obtained by relaxing some of these axioms; see Section 3.1.1.

Let $G = (V, E)$ be a fuzzy graph.

- Existence an (special) edge. A subset S of V is called a *nikfar dominating set* in G , if for every $v \in V - S$, there is $u \in S$ such that uv be a special edge.
- assigning to every vertex a number obtaining a summation of its values with summation its edge's values to all its edge's values. For every $u \in V$, the *nikfar weight* of u is defined by $w_n(u) = \sigma(u) + \frac{d_s(u)}{d(u)}$. If $d(u) = 0$, for some $u \in V$. Then we consider $\frac{d_s(u)}{d(u)}$ equal with 0. For any $S \subseteq V$, natural extension of this concept to a set, is as follows. We also say the *nikfar weight* of S , it is defined by $w_n(S) = \sum_{u \in S} (w_n(u))$.
- The set has the minimum number is an optimal set. Now, let U be the set of all dominating sets in G . The *nikfar domination number* of G is defined as $\gamma_n(G) = \min_{D \in U} (w_n(D))$. The dominating set that is correspond to $\gamma_n(G)$ is called by *nikfar dominating set*.

4 Algebraic and arithmetic domination

By regrading to $E(G)$, we can define several types of a edge. In other words, this notion would give several labels.

Definition 4.1 (several types of edges). Let $G = (V, E)$ be a fuzzy graph. Let $e = xy$ be an edge. $E(G - e)$ would be (it is trivial) a fuzzy graph obtained from deleting the edge e .

- If $E(e) = E(G - e)$, then e is called an edge type-I.
- If $E(e) > E(G - e)$, then e is called an edge type-II.
- If $E(e) \geq E(G - e)$, then e is called an edge type-III.
- If $E(e) < E(G - e)$, then e is called an edge type-IV.
- If $E(e)$ be equal to the minimum $V(x)$ and $V(y)$, then e is called an edge type-V.
- If $E(e) \leq E(G - e)$, then e is called an edge type-VI.

Definition 4.2 (Nikfar Domination). Let $G = (V, E)$ be a fuzzy graph.

- If there is an type-I. This edge would introduce *nikfar domination type-I*.
- If there is an edge type-II. This edge would introduce *nikfar domination type-II*.
- If there is an edge type-III. This edge would introduce *nikfar domination type-III*.
- If there is an edge type-IV. This edge would introduce *nikfar domination type-IV*.
- If there is an edge type-V. This edge would introduce *nikfar domination type-V*.
- If there is an edge type-VI. This edge would introduce *nikfar domination type-VI*.
- If there is an edge. This edge would introduce *nikfar domination type-VII*.

We can also start discussions about the numbers of these special edges introducing the new structures.

5 Connections

Appendix

References

1. M. Nikfar, *Nikfar Domination in Fuzzy Graphs*, Preprints2019, 2019010024 (doi: 10.20944/preprints201901.0024.v1).